

A LOOK AT THE HISTORY OF STUDYING THE PSYCHOLOGICAL ADAPTATION OF PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract. *Transferring knowledge on any subject involves creating educational tasks. When teaching psychology, pedagogical and psychological tasks are identified and solved. Pedagogical activity consists mainly of solving didactic and educational tasks aimed at resolving contradictions in the learning process.*

From the list of functions, the necessary knowledge from various branches of psychology, as well as pedagogy, becomes obvious. The methodology of teaching psychology uses knowledge of psychology, on the one hand, and pedagogy, on the other. Pedagogy and methodology are related as a generic and specific concept. Pedagogy determines the general patterns of training and education, and methodology interprets them in relation to its subject.

Keywords: *psychology, pedagogy, motivation, history of education, upbringing, methodology.*

Teaching methodology as a science considers the question of the goals and objectives of teaching psychology. Without an answer to this question, it cannot solve other issues. For a certain time, the goal of teaching was considered to be equipping students with psychological knowledge, skills and abilities. At present, the role of science is increasing, the volume of knowledge is growing.

In the literature there are various ideas about the subject and object of the methodology of teaching psychology. Let's consider some of them.

1) The subject of MPP is teaching psychology, understood as a management process carried out by a teacher (lecturer), who uses a number of auxiliary means: textbooks, visual aids, technical teaching aids, etc. Teaching psychology is teaching psychological activity;

2) psychological education, teaching the basics of psychological science and the inextricable link to upbringing of the younger generation are the objects of the methodology;

3) the methodology of teaching psychology is the science of psychology as an academic subject and the laws of the process of teaching different age groups;

4) the methodology of teaching psychology is the science of psychology as an academic subject and the laws of the process of teaching different age groups;

5) the subject of didactics of psychology is psychological education, including training and related upbringing, as well as its problems and development prospects, while noting that the subject of didactics of psychology is the process and result of mastering subject program;

6) methodology is a section of pedagogy, i.e. scientists consider the subject of methodology, including training, education and upbringing, and sometimes limiting it to a set of means and methods for mastering the content of education. At the same time, they understand

learning differently, considering it either as an interaction between a teacher and students, or a process of mastering actions, or cognitive activity [4].

Therefore, it is important to instill in students the desire to independently acquire knowledge.

The methodology of teaching psychology as a science solves the issue of general patterns and didactic principles on the basis of which the process of teaching psychology is built. The methodology of teaching psychology considers the question "What to teach? What amount of knowledge to give to students at different levels of their training?". Despite the fact that the problem of developing a system of tasks for the learning process has not been studied for a very long time, there are several options for classifying pedagogical tasks.

All pedagogical tasks are divided into two types:

1. Theoretical tasks that do not require practical actions and are solved at the intellectual level.

In turn, theoretical tasks are divided into: 1) Analytical tasks that require the ability to analyze the actions of the teacher and students, identify the main contradictions in the learning situation, understand its structure, and so on;

2) Evaluation tasks that help develop the ability to evaluate the actions of participants in a pedagogical situation; the student learns to apply theory to specific phenomena and develop his own position;

3) Tasks for choosing the right pedagogical action;

4) Tasks for predicting the course of the learning process or its result;

5) Tasks for finding pedagogical errors.

2. Practical, visual, developing pedagogical skills and abilities.

Khromenko O. V. describes another classification of pedagogical tasks:

1. Situational tasks that are formulated and then solved by analyzing a specific pedagogical situation.

2. Abstracted tasks that include a contradictory dialogue, a controversial statement, or a comparison of theoretical positions.

Taxonomy of learning objectives in teaching psychology. In 1956, B. S. Bloom and his colleagues published the first volume of "Taxonomy of educational objectives", developed and agreed upon with the American Council for Entrance Examinations into Colleges and Universities. B. S. Bloom gives two taxonomies: concerning the cognitive sphere and concerning the affective sphere. The principle of the taxonomy is the transition to solving problems of a more complex level after mastering problems of a simpler level [5-6]. Bloom's taxonomy of the cognitive domain contains six levels: knowledge, understanding, analysis, synthesis, evaluation. Bloom's taxonomy of the affective domain contains five levels: desire, response, evaluation, organization, preference based on value or value complex.

One of the most productive taxonomies is the taxonomy of D. Tollingerova, who studied the types of advanced learning management. Her position is close to the interpretation of the goals of learning management in the theory of the step-by-step formation of mental actions by P. Ya. Galperin and N. F. Talyzina[7].

The learning task is a type of advanced management of cognitive activity, a project of a future learning action that determines the intellectual space for performing mental actions. Advanced management of learning with the help of tasks that operationalize the acquired content

of knowledge, Tolingerova D. called project-based, in contrast to reflexive, associated with the selection and awareness of the subject of knowledge itself and the generalization of the methods of its own mental activity.

Learning objectives are a specification of learning goals, necessary for selecting appropriate methods and techniques. With their help, it is determined what exactly students should learn, and the content to be learned is operationalized. An interesting and constructive approach to classifying learning objectives was proposed by D. A. Tollingerova (1981); in relation to teaching psychology, this approach was revised by V. Ya. Lyaudis (1989) [9].

Learning tasks are divided into six classification groups according to cognitive characteristics:

- 1) the first group consists of tasks requiring the reproduction of knowledge;
- 2) the second - tasks requiring simple mental actions (description and systematization of facts);
- 3) the third - tasks for complex mental operations (argumentation, explanation);
- 4) the fourth - tasks that involve the generation of certain speech utterances to express a productive mental act (abstract, essay, original scientific text);
- 5) the fifth - tasks for productive thinking (problem solving). Within each group, subgroups of tasks are distinguished;
- 6) the sixth - reflexive tasks.

This taxonomy can be productively used for the typology of educational tasks in psychology. V. Ya. Lyaudis proposed to expand some groups of tasks in relation to teaching psychology, in particular the 4th and 5th groups. The tasks of the 4th group are interesting because they combine reproductive and productive forms of mental activity. In this regard, different types of psychological descriptions and explanations can be distinguished [10].

Thus, descriptions can take the form of a narrative, the form of a projection of logical relationships, and can be created using metaphors and other artistic thinking techniques. Explanations can be constructed using the apparatus of conceptual logical thinking (interpretation of symbols, use of symbolic analogs - a parable, a myth, an artistic image).

The fifth group of tasks was supplemented with new subgroups related to the specifics of psychology as an academic subject.

V. Ya. Lyaudis supplemented Tollinger's taxonomy with another group - reflexive tasks. These tasks provide a transition to metacognitive activity, i.e. to the conscious use of one's own methods of constructing heuristics, algorithms, and methods of analyzing open tasks. The peculiarity of the 6th group of tasks is that in order to solve them it is necessary to create a special situation of educational interaction[8]. This situation is characterized by the fact that students are faced with the need to recognize and identify their own methods of cognitive actions and consciously develop cognitive strategies for solving all types of problems. From the installation of subject knowledge, students move on to the installation of identifying the methods of their own mental activity. The listed tasks are solved using various teaching methods. First, let's consider the most significant stages in teaching psychology in high school. The beginning of teaching psychology in school dates back to 1811.

In European countries, psychology as a field of knowledge was studied within the framework of philosophy, as philosophical propaedeutics in close connection with logic. In the 19th century, psychology was studied during the school week in Australia for 2 hours, in Italy - 6,

in France - 8, in Germany - 2 hours. In the United States, psychology was included in the curriculum since the 1830s. American psychology was taught under the name mental philosophy. This course was replaced by a course in moral philosophy, which emphasized ethics, religion and moral development. By 1900, mental philosophy began to be replaced by psychology based on experimental psychology [10]. In Russia, according to the Charter of 1804, compulsory teaching of psychology was introduced into the gymnasium curriculum. The curriculum copied the curriculum of a foreign school.

Reasons holding back the development of teaching psychology in school:

- training was not related to real life;
- there were no adapted teaching aids;
- there was a shortage of trained teachers.

Since 1819, psychology was excluded from the curriculum. Later, psychology was included in the programs on logic and philosophy.

At the beginning of the 20th century, American philosopher John Dewey proposed a reform of the American educational system and considered psychology as a means of "mental hygiene". According to Benjamin, 2001, in 1937, psychology was taught in 12% of schools, and 37% supported the introduction of this subject.

In Russia, since 1905, a course in psychology and philosophy was introduced in gymnasiums, thanks to Professor G. I. Chelpanov, who prepared a textbook - the main manual for gymnasiums [11].

In 1916, A. P. Nechaev, in his report "On Teaching Psychology in Secondary School", made at the III All-Russian Congress on Experimental Pedagogy, called on the congress "to take measures to ensure that gymnasiums have psychology teachers with sufficient specialized training". A. P. Nechaev published the book "How to Teach Psychology? Methodological Guidelines for Teachers of Secondary Educational Institutions". Of particular interest is the work of F. F. Oldenburg "Thoughts on the Organization of Teaching Psychology in Secondary School" [12].

After the October Revolution, due to the reorganization of secondary schools, psychology disappeared from school programs. And it was reintroduced only in 1947. In accordance with the resolution of the Central Committee of the All-Union Communist Party (Bolsheviks) "On the Teaching of Logic and Psychology in Secondary Schools", psychology was introduced in 598 schools. A textbook prepared by Professor B. M. Teplov was published. But since 1958, psychology as a compulsory subject was again excluded. It began to be actively included as an optional subject in the 80s of the 20th century.

Thus, the main reasons holding back the introduction of psychology teaching in the secondary level of the education system were:

- a shortage of appropriate educational and methodological support;
- a shortage of teaching staff;
- changes in the goals of secondary education.

The statutes of universities have been repeatedly amended, which has affected the composition of the disciplines taught. Psychology, like philosophy, has been excluded from the program for many years and then reinstated after some time. Naturally, over these years, personnel and accumulated teaching experience have been lost.

The teaching of psychology in secular educational institutions was for a long time strongly influenced by the traditions that had developed within the framework of theological education. In the theological school, psychology as a subject was introduced almost a century earlier than in the secular school, and the teaching process was more stable. Theological academies also provided for the training of psychology teachers. At the first Moscow University, psychological knowledge was taught within the framework of other disciplines. Lomonosov in his book "Rhetoric", published in 1748, outlined the teachings on passions, close to the concept of Spinoza. In later manuals, psychological aspects were considered in more detail.

For example, in the work of A. Glagolev "Speculative and Experimental Foundations of Literature" (1834) had a section entitled as follows: "The Theory of Literature, Derived from the Principles of Psychology". This section examined the following questions: "On the Abilities of the Soul", "On the Talents of an Artist, Poet, and Writer in General", "On the Triplicity of Goals and Objects of Rhetoric, Derived from the Three Forces of the Mind". Psychology was also considered as an integral part of the philosophy course [13].

The matter was complicated by the fact that teachers read their courses in German or Latin. The charter of January 12, 1755 left the question of lecturing in Russian or Latin open. Russian professors preferred to lecture in Latin, since the manuals were written in Latin. In addition, this was considered a sign of scholarship and good manners. Students knew these languages poorly. Therefore, the effectiveness of such teaching was low.

The content of the philosophy and psychology courses was far from life. In this regard, there were few people willing to study these disciplines, much less prepare to teach them [14].

In 1796, Mikhailov's "Science of the Soul" was published in Russia - the first original attempt to systematize psychological knowledge. According to B. G. Ananyev, "Mikhailov's psychological treatise was written in the spirit of a seriously understood English empiricism".

In 1815, a book by the master of the local university P. Lyubovsky, "A Brief Guide to Experimental Psychology", was published in Kharkov.

Lyubovsky's work consisted of three parts: 1) sensitivity; 2) cognition; 3) desire, attraction, will.

A little later, a manual by Professor P. Ladius was published. It was a course in logic, which had a long and somewhat pompous title, "Logical Instructions Guiding to the Knowledge and Distinction of the True from the False". The preface to the book gave a short course in psychology. These psychological chapters spoke about the soul and body, the faculties of the soul, imagination, mind, reason, desire, memory, the difference between minds and gymnastics of minds; about 30 pages were devoted to these issues, on which the basic concepts of psychology were very briefly defined on the basis of Wolffian psychology.

The teaching of psychology was affected by the persecution of philosophy as a science "extremely dangerous in political and religious terms". According to the regulation of October 14, 1827, only the teaching of logic, psychology, and the history of philosophy was permitted. According to the following university charter (1835), philosophy was not studied as a separate subject. The teaching of philosophy by secular professors was ordered to be abolished, and the teaching of courses on logic and psychology was assigned to professors of theology.

In 1834, A. I. Galich's major work, "The Picture of Man", was published. According to B. G. Ananyev, Galich's book differed from the theological standard of psychological works of that time. At Moscow University, in connection with the reorganization of the philosophy faculty in

1850, the philosophy department was abolished and its teaching ceased; only logic and psychology "survived". The teaching of these courses was assigned to professors of theology.

On February 22, 1860, a regulation was approved on the restoration of the departments of the history of philosophy, logic and psychology at universities. In 1861, the philosophy department was restored at the historical and philological faculty of Moscow University. Professor P. D. Yurkevich was appointed its head. Since psychology, along with logic, ethics and the history of philosophy, was considered one of the philosophical disciplines, Yurkevich also taught a course on psychology. But only the charter of 1863 fully restored the teaching of philosophy and psychology at universities.

The consequence of the expulsion of philosophy from universities was, first of all, the loss of teaching staff. The first problem that universities faced when restoring the departments of philosophy, logic and psychology was the search for and training of staff. The open departments were again occupied by people who had a theological education. There were no specific requirements for the construction of programs for teaching psychology at universities, so each teacher put into the course the content that he considered necessary depending on his interests and level of training.

The content of the psychology course that Troitsky taught at Moscow University was determined by the ideas of English empirical psychology. This was a big step forward compared to the courses that were taught before him (Yurkevich) and after him (Lopatin). The teaching activity of M. M. Troitsky was of great importance for the development of psychological science in Russia. In his works that appeared in the 1980s, Troitsky defended the position of psychology as an independent science. He believed that psychology as a science of the spirit should study the facts of consciousness using scientific (positive) methods, and above all subjective analysis, i.e. self-observation.

Professor N. Ya. Grot was the first to use a seminar as a form of teaching psychology. This was a great innovation for university teaching. Three types of seminars were held. At the first type of seminar, he invited the listeners to criticize the lecture he had given. He willingly listened to the comments of his young listeners and entered into a dispute with the audience. Seminars of this type were directly connected with the psychology course. Grot also had another type of seminar, in which he offered listeners topics for essays. There was no specific system in choosing topics. Grot did not always take into account the level of difficulty of the topics given to students. He proceeded from the opinion that there were no topics that were too difficult for students.

At the third type of seminar, students presented theses, which were read out and discussed in the audience. Psychology was also taught as part of medical education. In 1888, a psychological laboratory was created at the Psychiatric Clinic of Moscow University by A. Ya. Kozhevnikov, which was headed at various times by S. S. Korsakov, A. A. Tokarsky, N. A. Bernstein, and F. E. Rybakov. The laboratory became the basis for practical classes that were part of the psychology course taught by Associate Professor of Psychiatry, A. A. Tokarsky.

In general, it can be said that the teaching of psychology during this period played an educational role and did not prepare for independent research or practical work.

Since the early 1940s, psychology departments were opened at the philosophy departments of a number of universities, and thus, for the first time, the training of professional psychologists began. In 1941, the philosophy department was restored as part of Moscow University, where the psychology department was established in 1942. Professor S. L. Rubinstein was appointed its head.

Since 1951, the psychology department at the university was headed by A. N. Leontiev, who continued to improve psychological education[15].

The system of higher psychological education also began to develop at Leningrad University. V. N. Myasishchev and A. V. Yarmolenko participated in the creation of the psychology department. A significant milestone in the history of teaching psychology was the publication of a number of textbooks. In 1966, psychology departments were opened at several universities: first at Moscow and Leningrad, and then at Yaroslavl and Tbilisi universities. The independent status of psychology departments allowed for the expansion of the possibilities of psychological education. The number of psychological disciplines taught increased significantly.

Since the 1965/66 academic year, medical psychology has been taught in medical universities across the country.

In the 1965/66 academic year, special courses in legal psychology began to be taught in law schools in Moscow, Leningrad, Minsk and some other cities.

A significant event for postgraduate psychological education was the fact that in 1968, the Higher Attestation Commission singled out psychological sciences from the general composition of pedagogical sciences into an independent group and included psychology in the list of branches of science for which academic degrees are awarded.

In 1997, there were already 90 psychology departments in Russia. The training of psychologists according to the full university program has become widespread [3]. At the same time, the number of educational programs in which psychology was studied as an additional specialty was expanding, and the number of psychology courses for students of other specialties was increasing.

The goals, duration, structure and content of psychology training are largely determined by national education systems, historical traditions, the level of development and status of psychology as a science in a particular country, economic and political factors.

Thus, a certain idea of the main areas of modern psychology can also be given by the library-bibliographic classification, knowledge of which can be useful for psychologists when working with literature on any problem in library catalogues.

Depending on the research method or psychological practice, such branches of psychology as scientific and practical psychology, experimental psychology, mathematical psychology, psychodiagnostics, psychotherapy, and consulting psychology are distinguished. It is natural to assume that the listed branches of psychology, areas of psychological research and psychological practice should be reflected to some extent in the curricula of psychological education.

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